

The Impact of Work Environment, Work Discipline, and Leadership towards Employees' Performance in Improving Rural Area Development

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Abstract:

Indonesia is a country with a very large number of villages, based on the initial data of the year 2019, the number reaches 83,931 villages and spread over 13,466 inhabited islands from approximately 17,000 existing islands. As the lowest governmental administration area, the dynamic growth of the village will have a stimulant impact on the development of broader areas of the region, so that all realize national prosperity, the thing to do is to do development equality in rural areas. The task of management of this rural development equality program is located at the Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and the Transmigration Republic of Indonesia. This study was conducted to uncover factors that have a significant influence on the performance of employees who are directly addressing the work. The research was conducted during 2019-2020 using quantitative research approaches and observations. The results of data using multiple linear regression showed that the most influential factors significantly on the performance of the staff of Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and the Transmigration Republic of Indonesia were Work Discipline, followed later by Leadership and factors that are the least impact of the Work Environment.

Keyword: Work Environment, Discipline, Leadership, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of rural areas in Indonesia, which is an archipelago with a fairly dense population in fairness and equitable, is a prerequisite for the Government of the Republic of Indonesia to become a prosperous and equitable country. Therefore, the development of rural areas must be governed by those who do have not only the competence for it but also has a commitment and discipline as well as an important thing is leadership ability.

From the preliminary research, we conducted in early April 2019 to 62 staff Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and the Transmigration Republic of Indonesia. There are at least three main factors perceived by the employees that are very influential in the spirit of work, loyalty, and even commitment to do the best work, namely Work Environment, Discipline, and Leadership. On the basis of these preliminary research results, further research is done to uncover the factors that most influence the performance of staff Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and the Transmigration Republic of Indonesia. Keeping in mind that the Indonesian Government is currently continuing to launch an equitable development in all villages throughout Indonesia, while the number of staff who do management and management of village development and rural areas is very limited.

The working environment is everything that is around workers at work, both physical and non-physical structure that can influence a representative at work. On the off chance that the workplace that representatives can be sheltered, agreeable, and if the workplace doesn't bolster, the worker cannot securely and easily (Devita et al., 2019; Runeson et al., 2011; Alfiyah, 2019). Over the last 27 years, the demand-control-support model developed by Karasek and expanded by Johnson and Hall and others have dominated the research on the relationship between the work environment and health (Simmons & Swanberg, 2009; Baik et al., 2019). A good work environment will motivate employees to work more optimally because they feel comfortable and are supported by the company. This comfortable feeling can reduce the stress and boredom experienced by employees towards their work. In achieving performance and goals that are targeted by the company, a conducive work environment is considered very important to be considered by the company so that the performance of employees reaches the optimal point as expected by the company (Asriani, 2020; Bohle et al., 2011). Since the emergence of theoretical approaches in the field of work

motivation in the 20th century, several models have linked job characteristics and factors in the work environment to performance (Bipp, 2010; Claudia Figari, 2011; Choi et al., 2011).

The transition from a non-high-strain job toward a high-strain one was associated with a significant increase in fatigue but that a reverse transition toward a non-high-strain job was not related to a reduction of fatigue (Wahlstedt et al., 2010). The essence of a practice school is to supplement traditional classroom learning and "instructions" with practice-based learning (PBL) and "constructionism," which together can be succinctly described as "learning by doing." This learning takes place at industrial sites in a real work environment where students are trained to solve real-life problems (Keleher et al., 2011). Work environments that entail high levels of manager-controlled flexible scheduling necessitate that workers actively and constantly beg managers for schedules to be altered and more hours granted (Wood, 2018).

Etymologically, the word discipline comes from the Latin word, meaning followers. Through time, this word changes to "discipline," which means obedience or anything related to the rules. Discipline is related to the employees who come and go on time, do the job appropriately, obey the rules of the organization or norms shared among the community (Liwijaya, 2019).

Work Discipline in a variety of previous studies is always associated with the issue of fairness and reasonable punishment (Bugdol, 2018; Furlong, 2008; Esbester, 2008). Research by Dupper suggests that the work discipline is more as a pattern of self-control behavior as well as a discipline as a result of external control (Dupper, D. R. 2010; Hibou, B. 2009).

Due to the nature of the work discipline contributed from these internal and external aspects, many believe that working discipline is a thing that can be taught, controlled and even can be changed or repaired (Egan & Thompson, n.d.; Falcone, 1999; Clark & Nye, 2018; Jones, 2009).

The above considerations ultimately give confidence that in principle, the organization can intervene its officers to learn and be able to exercise anything that he or she should make appropriate to the demands of the organization or in other words always improve the ability to discipline themselves following the developments that occurred (Lynch, 2015; Knight, 2016) and for this reason, the management of work discipline in the context of human resource management is not negligible (Grieves, 2003).

In an organization, leadership roles cannot be ignored. Leaders are navigators who must provide direction and simultaneously demonstrate various obstacles to avoid, build joint commitments, and take risks for organizational advancement (Martin & O'Sterling, 2014; Maestro, 2020). In connection with the task of a leader, many studies of existing leadership types such as transformational, transactional, or laissez-faire styles (Piotrowski, 2018). Leaders need to develop leadership styles that enable them to react quickly to change, involving followers to try new ideas, and create a safe environment that enables risk-taking. Flexible leadership styles are effective in meeting the demand for solutions to difficult problems faced by organizations (Taylor et al., 2019).

Leadership is crucial that is very decisive for growing and growing an organization because it is the one who creates and while maintaining the consistency of achievement of the vision and mission of an organization. Leaders are those who are leading in the determination of what and how they should learn to utilize every developmental opportunity (Tremaine, 2010; Allen, 2016). Indeed in an organization, a leader is expected to be able to quickly adapt to the opportunities and threats that exist, take the endeavor and build a competitive organization and become a role model in the problem of ethics (Thomson et al., 2017; Elçi et al., 2012).

Today we live in an integrated world, global leadership in organizations that tend to globalized and networks, fundamentally different conditions of leadership in the traditional hierarchy. So, how the interaction between culture and leadership develops as the world becomes more globally interconnected is one of the prerequisites for successful leadership in the organization as well, alongside a global understanding of ethical leaders (Schein, 2010; Shin, 2012).

In the context of disciplining employees, good leadership is able to establish employee discipline from the internal side, which triggers a delegative leadership style and offers little or no special guidance that leads to inadequate decisions unless a member highly qualifies themselves in the relevant case (Hay, 2010; Eisenbeiß & Boerner, 2013). This condition is also conveyed by Chi which beliefs in the important role of Transformational Leadership in building team processes, and the team's performance is achieved through the strengthening of teamwork discipline (Chi et al., 2011). McManus's research on generation Millennial workers also showed similar results to what Chi examined, where the known millennials were not

easily regulated to be relatively very disciplined when in good and persuasive leadership (McManus Warnell, 2015).

The performance of employees in various research conducted proved very influential on the achievement of organizational performance. From the available evidence, employees with good performance on average provide better returns for investors, have customers who use their products more, have more satisfied customers, lower turnover rates, low absenteeism, and high working discipline (Roberts, 2005). The performance of these good employees is essentially the end result of how their competence with a combination of commitments to the duties of responsibility they do (Griffiths, n.d.; Merriman, 2017).

Employee performance is usually measured by the productivity and efficiency of work generated by an employee, the measurement results in input for the organization in establishing the necessary training needs, setting strategic objectives even as a feed-back material for each individual in the organization about the level of competence, commitment, attitude, talents or other things that are worthy of their knowledge (Veda Prakash et al., 2016; Latukha, 2018; Shaw & Allen, 2009).

Some nonprofit organizations also use the measurement of employee performance that further emphasizes the level of employee suitability with the culture of the organization they are interested in and how high their stakeholder satisfaction has gained. The performance value of employees in the non-profit organization is crucial to establish conformity between positions or existing positions with the qualifications of those who will be appointed to fill the position (Maestro, 2020; Estell et al., n.d.).

One of the things that are also a measure of employee performance, according to Ennals is the level of ability of employees to take the initiative to change with risks laden with additional responsibilities (Ennals, 2018). Similarly, the level of commitment of the organization (Reio & Ghosh, 2009), as well as the interests and talents that exist (Al Hashmi et Al., 2019).

It can generally be said that the main indicators of the organization's performance will be heavily influenced by how good and quality the officer exists, and it is demonstrated by the performance of employees in the organization (Ellis & Tsang, 2010), this is only possible if the organization has the capability to manage both Sumer human resources, since the recruitment, education and training process, and the implementation of the ability to directly involve employees with a high level of discipline in co-starring the problems faced by an organization (Sun et al., 2004).

1.2 Research Objectives

The objective of the research is to identify the factors that directly or indirectly affect employee performance in The Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and The Transmigration Republic of Indonesia. Further to examine whether the employee performance can be improved by approach and improvement on the factors discussed in this research, namely Work Environment, Work Discipline, and Leadership, and how much the factors influence each other.

1.3 Research Methodology and Data Analysis

This type of research is using quantitative analysis that uses primary data in the form of surveys. This study design to be able to understand, explain, and analyze the correlation between independent variables on the dependent variable. The number of items measured in dimensions and indicators of independent (exogenous) variables in the form of the Work Environment (WE), Work Discipline (WD), and Leadership (L) while the dependent variable (endogenous) is Employee Performance (EP) can see in Table 1:

Table 1: Operational Definitions of Research Variables

Research Variable	Dimension	Research Indicator
Work Environment (WE)	1. Physical Work Environment	a) Lighting
		b) Air
		c) Noise
		d) Security
		e) Cleanliness
		f) Completeness of work facilities
		g) Condition of working tools

	2. Non-physical Work Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Work responsibilities b) Attention and support of leaders c) Cooperation between groups d) Smooth communication e) Work structure
Work Discipline (WD)	1. Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Leadership models can establish discipline b) Can control speech, actions, and attitudes. c) The role of the leader model has a significant influence on the organization
	2. Providing Compensation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Providing compensation affects discipline b) Comply with all applicable rules c) Receive adequate compensation d) Feeling the payment received is far from adequate
	3. Definitive Rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Fostering discipline cannot be carried out if there are no written rules b) The subject is not possible to enforce if regulations based on instructions c) Want to discipline if there are rules
	4. Taking action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Supervision will direct employees to carry out work appropriately and adequately b) Always want to be free not bound c) Upright discipline is necessary so as not to do as you wish
Leadership (L)	1. Idealized Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Leaders foster confidence and trust in subordinates b) Leaders are admired and become role models
	2. Inspirational Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The leader articulates a compelling vision of the future b) Speak optimistically with enthusiasm c) Give encouragement and meaning to what needs to done
	3. Intellectual Stimulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Encourage the expression of ideas from subordinates b) Leaders encourage innovative thinking c) Involve subordinates in decision making
	4. Individual considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Consider the needs of subordinates, abilities, and aspirations. b) Listen Attentively. c) Advising, Teaching, and Training.

A. Population and Sample

The population in this study is all employees of The Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and The Transmigration Republic of Indonesia with the position of Echelon III amounted to 98 people. The sampling techniques in this study used saturated samples or census techniques.

B. Method of collecting data

Data sources used are primary data in the form of surveys, questionnaires, and secondary data in the form of employee performance achievements, employee attendance lists, and interviews with relevant and competent officials within The Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and The Transmigration Republic of Indonesia.

C. Data Analysis Method

Activities in data analysis are grouping data based on variables and types of respondents, tabulating data based on variables from all respondents, presenting data for each variable studied, and doing calculations to answer the problem formulation and doing calculations to test the hypothesis that has to propose.

Data analysis performs descriptively and quantitatively. Descriptive analysis is carried out with the help of the Microsoft Excel program to find out the description of Work Environment, Discipline, Leadership, and Employee Performance. In contrast, quantitative analysis is carried out using multiple linear regression methods and using the SPSS 24.0 tool to test the relationship between variables.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Based on Table 2 below, it can see that the characteristics of The Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and The Transmigration Republic of Indonesia.

Characteristics of respondents by sex, it is known that most respondents were 77 people (78.57%), and 21 women (21.43%). While the respondents' characteristics according to years of service, it was found that those who had worked between 3 and 5 years were 67 people (67%), and the working period was less than three years as many as 31 people (31%).

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents

Description	Frequency (Person)	Presentation (%)
Gender		
Male	77	78.57
Woman	21	21.43
Years of Service		
Less than 3 years	31	31
3 - 5 years	67	67

Source: Directorate General of Rural Area Development, 2019.

B. Validity Test

Table 3: Validity Test

No	r-count WE	r-table	Info	r-count WD	r-table	Info	r-count L	r-table	Info	r-count EP	r-table	Info
1	.492**	> 0.196	Valid	.783**	> 0.196	Valid	.680**	> 0.196	Valid	.622**	> 0.196	Valid
2	.581**	> 0.196	Valid	.841**	> 0.196	Valid	.802**	> 0.196	Valid	.627**	> 0.196	Valid
3	.579**	> 0.196	Valid	.780**	> 0.196	Valid	.793**	> 0.196	Valid	.710**	> 0.196	Valid
4	.652**	> 0.196	Valid	.718**	> 0.196	Valid	.713**	> 0.196	Valid	.661**	> 0.196	Valid
5	.372**	> 0.196	Valid	.804**	> 0.196	Valid	.722**	> 0.196	Valid	.576**	> 0.196	Valid
6	.627**	> 0.196	Valid	.797**	> 0.196	Valid	.725**	> 0.196	Valid	.629**	> 0.196	Valid
7	.611**	> 0.196	Valid	.788**	> 0.196	Valid	.689**	> 0.196	Valid	.637**	> 0.196	Valid
8	.532**	> 0.196	Valid	.656**	> 0.196	Valid	.693**	> 0.196	Valid	.638**	> 0.196	Valid
9	.414**	> 0.196	Valid	.691**	> 0.196	Valid	.671**	> 0.196	Valid	.608**	> 0.196	Valid
10	.570**	> 0.196	Valid	.783**	> 0.196	Valid	.738**	> 0.196	Valid	.594**	> 0.196	Valid

Based on Table 3 of the Validity Test Results above, it can seem that for the variable Work Environment (WE), Work Discipline (WD), Leadership (L) and Employee Performance (EP) which consists of forty questions, has a value of $r_{count} > r_{table} = 0.196$. Thus, the variable Work Environment, Work Discipline, Leadership, and Employee Performance, which consists of forty indicators of questions declared valid.

C. Reliability Test

Table 4: Reliability Test

Variable	Value Cronbach's Alpha	Terms	Info
Work Environment	0.731	> 0.6	Reliable
Work Discipline	0.780	> 0.6	Reliable
Leadership	0.772	> 0.6	Reliable
Employee Performance	0.756	> 0.6	Reliable

Based on Table 4, The Reliability Test results can see that for the variable Work Environment (WE), Work Discipline (WD), Leadership (L), and Employee Performance (EP) variables have Cronbach's Alpha values all above 0.6. Thus the variable Work Environment (WE), Work Discipline (WD), Leadership (L), and Employee Performance (EP), declared reliable.

D. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

Multiple linear regression analysis uses to determine the effect of the independent variable with the dependent variable. The use of multiple linear regression because this study uses more than one independent

variable, namely Work Environment (WE), Work Discipline (WD), Leadership (L), and Employee Performance (EP) on Employees of The Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and The Transmigration Republic of Indonesia.

Table 5: Test Analysis of Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
1 (Constant)	1.266	0.169	7.472	0.000
Work Environment	0.166	0.058	2.847	0.005
Work Discipline	0.390	0.044	8.801	0.000
Leadership	0.201	0.047	4.327	0.000

Correlations						
Variable	Dimension	Employee Performance				
		4.1 Quality of Work	4.2 Work Quantity	4.3 Employee Consistency	4.4 Employee Attitudes	
Work Environment	1.1 Non-Physical Work Environment	.430**	.422**	.481**	0.158	
	1.2 Physical Work Environment	.563**	.389**	.490**	.297**	
Work Discipline	2.1 Provision of Compensation	.716**	.594**	.636**	.614**	
	2.2 Leadership Model	.665**	.671**	.656**	.534**	
	2.3 Definitive Rules	.675**	.593**	.580**	.479**	
	2.4 Take Action	.517**	.484**	.393**	.396**	
Leadership	3.1 Charisma	.517**	.567**	.451**	.418**	
	3.2 Inspirational Motivation	.477**	.500**	.506**	.416**	
	3.3 Intellectual Stimulation	.501**	.489**	.601**	.453**	
	3.4 Individual Considerations	.417**	.412**	.510**	.415**	
N		98	98	98	98	

E. Correlation Between Dimensions

Table 6: Dimensions Correlations Result

Correlation analysis is a statistical analysis that measures the degree of the relationship involving more than one independent variable and one dependent variable. Variable correlation analysis use to determine the relationship between variables Work Environment, Work Discipline, and Leadership on Employee Performance.

Based on Table 6 above, it knows that the highest correlation value between dimensions in the Work Environment variable and Employee Performance variable is dimension 1.2 Physical Work Environment with a proportion of 4.1 Work Quality, 0.563. It includes in the category of relationship level that is on. It explains that the dimension 1.2 Physical Work Environment in the Work Environment variable is indispensable for any improvement in Employee Performance, especially in the Work Quality dimension.

The most excellent correlation between the dimensions in the Work Discipline variable and the Employee Performance variable is dimension 2.1 Giving compensation with aspects 4.1 of Work Quality that is 0.716 and falls into the category of healthy relationship levels. It explains that size 2.1 Giving reward in the Work Discipline variable is indispensable for any improvement in Employee Performance, especially in the Work Quality dimension. Meanwhile, the proportion with a low level of relationship is dimension 2.4 Taking Action on the Consistency dimension

Employees and Employee Attitudes. It explains that the Work Discipline variable influences the performance of the personnel, especially in the aspects of Compensation and Taking Action.

The most excellent correlation between the dimensions in the Leadership variable against the Employee Performance variable is the 3.3 Intellectual Stimulation dimension with the 4.3 Personnel Consistency dimension, which is 0.601 and belongs to the category of stable relationship levels. It explains

that the proportion 3.3 Intellectual Stimulation in the Work Environment variable is indispensable for any improvement in Employee Performance, especially in the Persistence of Employee Consistency dimension.

Conclusion

This research suggests that working disciplines have a very close relationship to employee performance, but the considerable influence is more derived from the reward system being applied. Thus, employees will demonstrate a good level of working discipline and ultimately affect employee performance, when discipline is related to the reward they will earn. This condition is certainly not in accordance with the main task of echelon officers 3 in the directorate that responsible for the efforts to equitable development of rural areas that many of them are remote areas and lagging. Exciting findings from this study, among others, at least the influence of employee performance is leadership, especially regarding individual considerations, including considering the needs of subordinates, abilities, and aspirations; listen attentively; consultation, teaching, and training. This condition illustrates how weak the leader's role is in listening to and accommodating subordination, coaching, counseling, and mentoring skills. This condition demonstrates the importance of soft competence improvement in the efforts of human resource development in the Directorate General of Rural Area Development, Ministry of Villages, Disadvantaged Regions, and The Transmigration Republic of Indonesia.

Another distinctive result in this study was that the non-physical work environment turned out to have the lowest level of influence on the establishment of employee attitudes. This condition illustrates the responsibilities of work that is still not optimal, the attention and support of the leaders, inter-group cooperation, smooth communication, checked the work done by the organization to be able to form the desired employee attitude is not match with what is desirable. Thus, an organisation needs to be more serious in conducting organizational governance related to changing the attitude of employees in accordance with the vision and mission conducted by the organizational values that so that the Organization is assigned to be internalized through the implementation of governance that manages changed and measured as a pointing employee performance appraisals/assessment.

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